

Lumah si Zahir

The House of Zahir

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Niyah ondeh ondeh hih, en na si Zahir. Si Zahir tihbet ag langeg ma halamn lumah sigam.
 There was once a child named Zahir. Zahir loved to play in the garden of their house.

Dakayoh llaw, tandah ag si Zahir niyah tomoh dawn gaddung ma bihing simintu sin pantan sigma.
 One day, Zahir noticed a green leafy plant that grew beside the cemented terrace of their house.

Pag llaw dakayoh na sab, indah na sab ag si Zahir in antan. Niyah na sab tomoh duwa na dawn gaddung.
 The next day, he has observed that the green leafy plant he saw increased in number. It became two.

Pag ika tallu llaw, niyah na mga sangpuh tandah na.
 On the third day, he saw that the green leafy plants became more than ten.

Katambunan na pinta lumah sigam.
 As the plants grew taller, it covered the paint of their house.

Paragan na iya ni rimay lumah.
 Zahir ran immediately inside their house.

"Inah! Paytu ba kau. Niyah pandah ku ma kau." Bah si Zahir.
 "Mom! Come here. I have something to show you." Zahir yelled.

"Ayyanan hih?" Bah inah na.
 "What is it?" Zahir's mother asked.

Pag ndah inah na, bah inah na, "In en na tu otoh, sempet."
 As Zahir's mother went out, she knew what she saw. "Oh this! This is called weeds, my son."

"Angay ian may an, inah? Bey tyanem ag nu?"
 "Why is it there, mom? Did you plant it?"

"Sah be otoh. Asal in sempet, minsan sah tyanem, tomoh iya."
 "No, son. That what weeds are. They grow even if you did not plant it."

"Na lupa na dagbes lumah ta, inah. Halaingga ag kalloan iya?"
 "Our house is ugly now, Mom. How can we remove it?"

"Halaytu." Hyublutan ag inah na kemon sin sempet hih. Lingkat na pabeyk in lumah sigam.
 "Like this." Zahir's mom pulled out the weeds from the soil one by one. It revealed the colorful paint of the house.

"Alloa! Lingkat na pa beyk inah in lumah ta."

"Nna halahih kau ag kalloan sempet. Subay kau jaga. Niyah niya tomoh hih, kalloan nu pasal bang pisaran, pamehe meen sampay katambunan meen lingkak sin lumah ta."

"Wow! Our house is now beautiful again!" Zahir exclaimed.

"That is how you remove weeds. You must be watchful. Every time there grows a weed, you have to pull it from the soil. Do not let it grow on its own because it will worsen and cover the beauty of our house."

"Ahoh, Inah." Bah si Zahir.
 "Yes, mom." Zahir understood.

Pag beyk, basta iya ag langeg, indah ag na bang niyah ka sempet. Killoan ag na.
 On the following days, every time he plays, he observes their terrace and looks for weeds. If he sees one, he immediately pulls it out.

Sampay iya pa mehe mehe na, haniyah misan dalamba sempet ma lumah sigam.
 Until he grew older, no number of weeds ever grew in their garden.

-End-

Note: The language used is Sama language. Sama language is in the municipality of Pangutaran, province of Sulu.

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